

CTBN / EPOXY / CARBON-BLACK NANO-COMPOSITES WITH IMPACT-ENERGY ABSORBABILITY

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SUMMARY

Composites consist of carboxyl-terminated butadiene acrylonitrile rubber (CTBN) / epoxy resin blends and carbon-black (CB) were formulated. The impact-energy absorbability of the composites depended on the kneading temperature of the resin and the CB. Strong interaction at the interface between CTBN and CB particles was the key factor to achieve the high impact-energy absorbability.

Keywords: rubber, epoxy, carbon-black, nano-composites, energy absorbability

1. INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins are widely used for structural adhesives in automotives, electronics and construction industries. With the increase of the application of fiber reinforced composites to those industries, the role of epoxy adhesives should increase for that the composites can not be welded. It would be desirable if the epoxy adhesives have more functionality such as damping performance or energy absorbability as well as the high adhesive strength.

In general, polymers are materials with damping performance especially at the glass-transition temperature, where the molecular motion and the friction of polymer chains convert given mechanical energy into thermal energy and dissipate it as heat release [1]. Homopolymers have narrow glass-transition regions, which cause the narrow temperature range with damping performance. One way to broaden the glass-transition regions is polymer blend [2]. Among many polymer blends, interpenetrating polymer networks (IPNs) were most studied to achieve the wide glass-transition regions [3-5], which related to the wide range of temperature with high damping performance. IPNs are defined as the intimate mixture of two or more cross-linked polymers in which one network is formed in the presence of another [6]. Ideally, interpenetration occurs only through physical mixing on a molecular scale, where no covalent bonds exist between the differing polymers [3]. Control of compatibility (morphology) and viscoelastic properties of the multi-component resin system would be the key to improve the damping performances.

The main components of the resins used in this study were an epoxy resin and a reactive liquid rubber: carboxyl-terminated butadiene acrylonitrile rubber (CTBN). We have indicated

that the CTBN / epoxy polymer blends have good adhesive properties and vibration damping performance [7, 8]. In the blends, all the components (epoxy monomers, reactive rubbers and curing agents) reacted with each other and generated covalent bonded networks. Therefore, the resulting network structures are out of the definition of IPNs above-mentioned. Although the combination of the epoxy resin and the CTBN is well known as the toughened epoxy systems [9], one of the differences of ours from others exists in the resin composition and the morphologies. Namely, the CTBN was used as the major component (60 wt %) of the blends, and the control of the compatibility among the components generated new categorized epoxy polymer alloys that possess both high damping and adhesive performances.

Vibration damping is an appearance of energy absorbability. Therefore, the CTBN / epoxy polymer blends are expected as materials with impact-energy absorbability also. In this paper, the impact-energy absorbability of the polymer blends and the composites reinforced by carbon-black (CB) particles is discussed. CB is well-known carbon nano-fillers used as reinforcing materials for elastomers. The objective of this study is to clarify the dominant factors that control the energy absorbability and the viscoelastic properties from viewpoints of the morphologies and the interaction among the components in the CTBN / epoxy / CB composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials

A carboxyl-terminated butadiene acrylonitrile (CTBN) rubber was used as the major components in resin compositions. The number average molecular weight of the CTBN was about 3500. The acrylonitrile (AN) contents in the CTBN was 26 mol%. Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A oligomers (DGEBA) were used as epoxy resins. The epoxy equivalents were 189 g / eq. Diamino diphenyl methane (DDM) was used as the curing agent. The chemical structures of these resin components were shown in Figure 1. Triphenyl phosphine (TPP) was used as a catalyst for the reaction between carboxyl groups in the CTBN and epoxies. The base resin formulation (weight ratio) was CTBN / DGEBA / DDM = 182 / 100 / 21, in which the CTBN was 60 wt% of the blends. Carbon-black (CB) particles with a primary diameter of 18nm were used as nano-fillers. It was known that the surfaces of CB particles can react with rubbers [10].

2.2. Pre-reaction between CTBN and epoxy resins

DGEBA, CTBN, and TPP as a catalyst were first mixed in a glass flask at 25°C and the temperature was raised to 160°C while stirring. The flask was kept at the same temperature in 2 hours for the pre-reaction between DGEBA and CTBN, then cooled down to room temperature.

2.3. Preparation of cured resins

In order to make cured resin specimens, CTBN / epoxy pre-reacted resin and DDM were mixed first and heated to 100°C to lower the viscosity of the resin, making it easier to disperse the DDM particles. Then, the resin compositions were held at 100°C under a vacuum to de-gas. The resin compositions were poured into preheated silicone-coated molds and cured at 130°C for 4 hours.

2.4. Preparation of CB reinforced composites

CB as nano-fillers was put into the CTBN / epoxy pre-reacted resin. The resins were kneaded by a twin screw kneader in 20min at 25°C, and the temperature was raised up to 100°C, 150°C,

or 200°C, then the CB / resin mixtures were kneaded in 30min at the same temperature. DDM as curing agent was mixed with the resin / CB compositions after cooling to below 80°C and degassed. The CB / resin composites were cured at 130°C for 4 hours in preheated silicone-coated molds.

2.5. Change of viscosity of uncured CTBN / DGEBA / CB at several temperatures

The rheological measurements were performed to detect the time-viscosity curves of uncured CTBN / DGEBA / CB composites under the shear stress at several temperatures, which models the kneading processes. The applied machine was a strain-controlled dynamic viscoelastometer (UBM, Co., Ltd., Rheosol-G5000NTD) with parallel plates as the fixtures. The diameter of the plates was 40mm and the gap distance was 300µm. The dynamic frequency of 1 Hz and the strain angle of 0.5 deg were applied at the test temperatures, i.e., 100°C, 150°C, or 200°C.

2.6. Quantification of “bound rubber” in uncured CTBN / DGEBA / CB

In case that the surfaces of CB particles have chemical reaction with oligomer molecules in the uncured resin, the reacted molecules would not be washed out from the surfaces of CB by solvents. In order to quantify the insoluble resin, i.e. “bound rubber”, the uncured resins after kneading with CB at 100°C, 150°C, or 200°C were diluted 20 times with acetone respectively, and filtered with a glass-fiber filter. After vacuum-drying at 50 °C in an oven, the acetone-insoluble residue was weighed. The weight percents of the insoluble residue on the basis of the each CB kneaded resin minus that of the residue from CB blended resin at 25 °C were expressed as the “bound rubber”.

2.7. Dynamic viscoelasticity of the cured resin and the CB reinforced composites

The temperature dependencies of the viscoelastic properties (storage modulus: E' , loss modulus: E'' and loss tangent: $\tan\delta$) of the cured resins were evaluated by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) in the tensile mode (span: 20 mm) at a dynamic frequency of 1 Hz and the amplitude of 10 µm using a viscoelastometer (Seiko Instruments, Inc., DMS6100) instrument. Cured resin specimens with a length of 45 mm, a width of 10 mm, and a thickness of 2 mm were machined from 2 mm-thick cured plaques. The samples were tested over a temperature range from -100°C to 150°C with a heating rate of 2°C /min.

2.8. Evaluation of tensile properties of the cured resin and the CB reinforced composites

Tensile properties of cured resins were evaluated at 25°C using JIS K 7113 at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min using the specimen in dog-bone shape. The dimensions of specimens were span length of 30 mm, width of 5 mm, and thickness of 2 mm.

2.9. Evaluation of energy absorbability of the cured resin and the CB reinforced composites

Impact-energy absorbability of the cured specimens was evaluated using a pendulum type impactor from 30°C to 70°C. A 200 g pendulum was dropped from 250 mm height (h_0) to samples, namely the given impact energy was 0.5 J. The dimensions of samples were length 45 mm, width 45 mm, and thickness 5 mm in total. After the impact loading, the pendulum was rebounded from the sample to a height (h). Then, the impact-energy absorbability E (%) was calculated by the next equation: $E = 100\{1 - (h / h_0)\}$.

2.10. Electron microscopy observation

2.10.1 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) for cured resins

Microtomed thin sections of the cured resins were stained by vapor of OsO₄ and observed using a scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) “JSM- 6340F” made by JEOL in reflected electron mode. The samples were mounted on brass stubs and were coated with a thin layer of platinum using an ion sputter coater. The OsO₄ stains the rubber-rich regions by depositing osmium in areas containing the unsaturated molecules, i.e., the butadiene in this study [11]. In the reflected electron mode, the OsO₄-stained regions were observed as bright areas.

2.10.2 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) for the CB reinforced composites

Thin sections were cryo-microtomed from the composites at -80 °C. The setting thickness was 40 - 50 nm. TEM images of the composites were obtained using a TEM (JEM-2100, Jeol) with 120 kV as acceleration voltage.

2.11. Scanning probe microscopy (SPM) for cured resins

In order to examine the nano structures, phase images of the surfaces of cured epoxy resins were obtained by “Tapping Mode” using SPM (Seiko Instruments, Inc., SPI3800N). A silicon cantilever SI-DF40 (Seiko Instruments, Inc.) with a dimension of 160 × 50 × 5 μm was used for the observation. The nominal tip radius is less than 10 nm, and the resonance frequency is around 300 kHz. The contrast in phase images (DFM images) is affected by the viscoelastic properties of the sample surface. A harder area gives more advanced phase and is shown in brighter color on this system.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Morphology of the cured matrix resin

First of all, the morphology of the matrix resin consists of CTBN / DGEBA / DDM was examined by electron microscopes. The reflected electron image by SEM of the resin was shown as Figure 2a. No clear phase structures were observed in the resin, in which the CTBN includes 26 mol% of AN. This is the morphology of the base matrix resin in this study. Meanwhile, a reference material was also shown as Figure 2b. Though the reference resin also had similar resin composition, the difference was the CTBN in the resin includes 18 mol% of AN. In this case, micro-phase separation was observed. The rubber-rich regions were shown as bright continuous area stained by OsO₄ and the epoxy-rich phases with diameters less than 1 μm were dispersed as relatively dark domains, as shown in Figure 2b. Namely, good compatibility among the components was achieved in the base matrix resin using the CTBN with 26 mol% of AN, as shown in Figure 2a. It should be noted that, however, true homogeneity would not be in the resin. Figure 3 shows a phase image by SPM of the resin. One can see some heterogeneity in nano-scale exists, though the precise characterization has not been achieved yet. This would mean the nature of each component (i.e., CTBN and DGEBA / DDM) still alive in nano-scale and would show different behavior in the polymer blends.

3.2. Viscoelastic properties of the cured matrix resin and the CB reinforced composites

The temperature dependencies of the viscoelastic properties (storage modulus: E' and loss tangent: tanδ) of the cured matrix resin consists of CTBN (with 26 mol% of AN) / DGEBA / DDM, and the 3 types of composites reinforced with CB (20 wt % in the composites) were examined, as shown in Figure 4. The peak top of tanδ of the matrix resin was 40 °C, and the

glass transition region was quite wide from under $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to over $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This suggests some heterogeneity exists in the matrix resin, which was pointed out in the above section also. Meanwhile, all 3 types of CB reinforced composites indicated higher E' than the matrix resin, especially in the rubbery region after the glass transition. The E' in the rubbery region of the CB composites kneaded at $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was somewhat higher than that of the CB composites kneaded at $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This suggests that the morphologies and the properties of the CB composites depended on the kneading temperature.

3.3. Tensile properties of the cured matrix resin and the CB reinforced composites

The tensile properties of the matrix resin (CTBN / DGEBA / DDM) and the composites with CB were evaluated, as shown in Figure 5. All 3 types of composites reinforced with CB showed higher strengths and moduli of elasticity than the matrix resin. The CB composites kneaded at 200°C showed the highest strength among them. Meanwhile, the modulus of elasticity of CB composites kneaded at $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was somewhat lower than that of CB composites kneaded at $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which corresponds to the tendency of E' from viscoelastic measurements in section 3.2.

3.4. Energy absorbability of the cured matrix resin and the CB reinforced composites

The impact-energy absorbability of the matrix resin (CTBN / DGEBA / DDM) and the 3 types of composites reinforced with CB were examined. The energy absorbability of the composites depended on the temperature for kneading the CTBN / DGEBA pre-reacted resin and CB particles, as shown in Figure 6. The energy absorbability of the composites with CB kneaded at 100°C or 150°C were lower than that of the matrix resin without CB. However, the energy absorbability of the composites kneaded at 200°C was higher than that of the matrix resin in wide range of temperature. Namely, the composites kneaded at 200°C had both high impact-energy absorbability and high modulus.

3.5. “Bound rubber” in kneaded mixtures consist of CTBN / epoxy resin and CB

In order to find the clue to explain the effect of the kneading conditions, the changes of viscosity were detected as time-viscosity curves on the kneading temperatures, shown in Figure 7. Only the case of measuring at 200°C , the viscosity of the CTBN / DGEBA / CB ternary mixture was clearly increased after a latent period. In cases of 100°C and 150°C , the change of viscosity was not shown. Figure 8 shows the time-viscosity curves of CTBN / CB binary mixture measured at 200°C . This indicated the similar behavior occurred between CTBN and CB. Meanwhile, DGEBA / CB binary mixture did not show the change of viscosity. These results suggest that strong interaction occurred mainly between CTBN and CB in kneading process at 200°C . Next, the amount of “bound rubber”, which was not washed-out from the surface of CB by acetone, was measured to quantify the interaction between CB and resin components in the CTBN / DGEBA / CB ternary mixtures by kneading. As shown in Figure 9, “bound rubber” (insoluble residue) on the CB surfaces increased with increasing the kneading temperature, and it was found that the CB composites kneaded at 200°C had the strongest interaction between CB and the resin components (mainly CTBN, connected with DGEBA and DDM molecules).

3.6. Morphologies of the CB reinforced composites

Figure 10 shows the difference in morphologies of CB reinforced composites observed by TEM. The composites kneaded at 100°C showed relatively homogeneous dispersion of CB

particles in the matrix resin. However, the CB particles were getting together with increasing the kneading temperature. In case of kneading at 200°C, many agglomerated CB domains of μm -size existed in the composites. From the magnified picture, it was found that the individual CB particles were largely covered with thin resin layer within the agglomerated CB domains, where the rubber-rich molecules would make chemical bonds with the surfaces of CB particles.

From these results, the mechanisms of impact-energy absorbability were assumed as below: “Bound rubber” formation between CB and rubber-rich molecules at 200°C enhanced the agglomeration of the resin-coated CB particles. In the agglomerated CB-resin domains, diversified resin molecules co-existed with a broad range of molecular motion level. Therefore, the molecular friction of polymer chains occurred effectively, which converted given mechanical energy into thermal energy and dissipated it as heat release.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Composites consist of carboxyl-terminated butadiene acrylonitrile rubber (CTBN) / epoxy resin blends as a matrix resin and carbon-black (CB) as nano-fillers were formulated.
2. The impact-energy absorbability of the composites depended on the kneading temperature of the resin and the CB. Formation of “bound rubber” (strong chemical interaction at the interface between the resin and CB particles) would be the key factor to achieve both the high impact-energy absorbability and the high strength of the composites.

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Figure 1 Chemical structure of resin components.

Figure 2 Morphologies of CTBN / DGEBA / DDM resins (reflected electron image of SEM after staining by OsO₄):
 (a) CTBN/DGEBA/DDM(182/100/21), AN in CTBN was 26mol%, as the matrix resin
 (b) CTBN/DGEBA/DDM(182/100/21), AN in CTBN was 18mol%, as a reference

Figure 3 Phase image of CTBN / DGEBA / DDM matrix resin by SPM (DFM mode):
 CTBN/DGEBA/DDM(182/100/21), AN in CTBN was 26mol%

Figure 4 Dynamic viscoelastic properties of the matrix resin and the CB (20 wt%) composites:
 ○, CTBN / DGEBA / DDM as the matrix resin
 □, CTBN / DGEBA / DDM / CB kneaded at 100°C ;
 ×, CTBN / DGEBA / DDM / CB kneaded at 150°C ;
 △, CTBN / DGEBA / DDM / CB kneaded at 200°C .

Figure 5 Tensile stress-strain behaviors of the matrix resin and CB composites:

- , CTBN / DGEBA / DDM as the matrix resin
- △, CTBN / DGEBA / DDM / CB (20 wt%) composites kneaded at 100°C ;
- ×, CTBN / DGEBA / DDM / CB (20 wt%) composites kneaded at 150°C ;
- , CTBN / DGEBA / DDM / CB (20 wt%) composites kneaded at 200°C.

Figure 6 Energy absorability of the matrix resin and CB composites :

- , CTBN / DGEBA / DDM as the matrix resin
- △, CTBN / DGEBA / DDM / CB (20 wt%) composites kneaded at 100°C ;
- ×, CTBN / DGEBA / DDM / CB (20 wt%) composites kneaded at 150°C ;
- , CTBN / DGEBA / DDM / CB (20 wt%) composites kneaded at 200°C.

Figure 7 Time-viscosity curves of CTBN / DGEBA / CB (20 wt%) ternary mixtures
 - Effect of kneading temperature - :
 ○, kneading temperature: 100°C ;
 ×, kneading temperature: 150°C ;
 ●, kneading temperature: 200°C .

Figure 8 Time-viscosity curves of
 CTBN / CB binary mixture; ●, DGEBA / CB binary mixture; ×, and CTBN / DGEBA / CB ternary mixture; ◆, kneading temperature: 200°C.

Figure 9 Relationship between the kneading temperature of CTBN / DGEBA / CB resins and the bound rubber content.

Figure 10 Morphologies of CTBN / DGEBA / DDM / CB composites (by TEM):
 - Effect of kneading temperature - :
 (a) (d) kneading temperature: 100°C ;
 (b) (e) kneading temperature: 150°C ;
 (c) (f) kneading temperature: 200°C.